

State of the art of the hardwood production in Europe and Spain and the challenges for a hardwoods-based sector in Galicia

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ABSTRACT

In the current market, the majority of wood products are derived from softwoods. However, the growing stock of hardwood trees and the increasing impact of climate change on forest adaptation represent a need to focus on hardwoods in view of long-term demand of main markets. This paper addresses key questions regarding the current state of European hardwood production and their main markets, the role of hardwoods in the construction sector, and the challenges that Galician hardwood forests are facing. The first section provides a quantitative overview of hardwood removals and the principal markets in Europe, Spain and Galicia. The second part of the study identifies the hardwood construction products currently manufactured in Spain. Finally, insights from a co-creation workshop revealed how regional stakeholders in forest management and different wood industries perceive and address the challenges of a hardwood-based forest sector in Galicia. The results indicate that the final use of hardwood removals for wood energy in Spain (16%) is below the EU-27 average (57%). It should be noted, however, that hardwood species account for only 20% of the total industrial roundwood. In Spain, the primary use for hardwood (mainly Eucalyptus spp. from Galicia) is the pulp and paper industry. Native broadleaved species account for just 1.3% of the Spanish hardwood harvesting volume. Nevertheless, we observe an emerging market for structural products in construction. Sweet chestnut, eucalyptus and beech have been structurally graded and are now included in the European standards, and a market for glulam beams from chestnut and oak is emerging. Among the main resilience challenges identified are fragmented forest properties and administrative barriers on hardwoods harvesting. The most promising solution for the region is seen in fostering more public-private cooperation between different actors along the whole value chain, to jointly develop feasible, adapted solutions and industrial investments in hardwoods processing and valorisation. Standardisation and co-design approaches can give promising impulses to boost hardwoods in the Galician green public procurement.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. EUROPEAN POLICIES AFFECTING WOOD CONSUMPTION

The European Union has set a goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050 through the decarbonisation of all industrial sectors. Several initiatives, strategies and policies are demanding for more sustainable materials and promoting circularity in the different value chains where wood and forest-based products have a role. Some affect all sectors, and others affect more directly certain value chains, such as the construction sector, such as the *Construction Products Regulation* (EU, 2022), the *Energy performance of Buildings Directive* (European Parliament, 2024), or the *New European Bauhaus initiative* (EU, 2024), which also concern other value chains, such as packaging, plastics, or textiles.

1.2. WOOD FLOWS IN EU-27

The main European (EU-27) wood industries (sawmill, wood-based panels and pulp) rely on primary resources, i.e. harvested timber from forest (Figure 1). The wood-based panels and pulp industries also use a share of by-products in their production. The main markets for sawmill and wood-based panel products are construction, furniture and

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wood packaging, while pulp is mainly destined for paper and paper packaging. In 2017, the sawmill industry was the main user of industrial roundwood (all roundwood except wood fuel), measured in cubic metres of solid wood equivalent (m^3 SWE), accounting for 54% of the total. The pulp industry came in second with 32%, while the wood-based panels industry accounted for 14%. However, these figures vary considerably depending on the country and the wood species in question.

Figure 1. Sankey diagram of the wood flows in EU-27 in 2017 (European_Commission, 2023)

1.3. GROWING STOCK IN WOOD SUPPLY IN FORESTS

Over the past 30 years, Europe's forest area has expanded by 9% and the volume of wood in European forests has grown by 50%, because the harvesting levels remain below the annual increment: about three-quarters of the net annual wood increment is harvested. The growing stock of broadleaved species increased at a higher rate than that of coniferous species (1.6% per year versus 1.2% per year) (Forest Europe, 2021).

The growing impacts of climate change (droughts, wildfires, storms, floods, pests, etc.) are affecting the adaptation of forests and the wood supply could be affected in a near future (Patacca et al., 2023). The prevalence of spruce (*Picea abies*) in European forests, representing approximately 20% of the biomass stock (Schelhaas et al., 2018), is being affected by beetle attacks. In the long term, this poses a risk for the availability of this main species used in construction and may limit sufficient volumes available for the market but may also offer opportunities for other species. Furthermore, the higher prevalence of fungi in the trees following the beetle attacks can negatively impact on wood properties, as observed in Czech forests (Hlásny et al., 2021), and may cause turbulence in wood markets of affected countries (Asada et al., 2023). Considering the need to mitigate the effects of climate change, it is becoming increasingly important to diversify the tree species used in forestry. The European forests' hardwood growing stock represents an opportunity to gain knowledge and address this diversification.

1.4. OBJECTIVE

This paper addresses several key questions regarding the current state of European hardwood production and their main markets, the role of hardwoods in the construction sector, and the challenges facing Galician hardwood forests. To this end, the case of Galicia, a typical hardwoods forest region in northwestern Spain, was studied. The work is structured into three parts. The first section provides a quantitative overview of hardwood removals and the principal markets in Europe, Spain and Galicia. The second part of the study identifies the hardwood construction products currently manufactured in Spain. Finally, insights from a co-creation workshop were analysed to reveal how regional stakeholders representing forest management and different wood industries and end-users perceive and address the current and future challenges of a hardwood-based forest sector in Galicia.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. HARDWOOD PRODUCTION AND MARKETS

The FAOSTAT statistical database (FAO, 2023) was analysed for the outlook in removals and wood production. The dynamics of removals and production by industry were analysed and the annual rate (%) of increase/decrease in production was calculated based on Equation 1 from the linear regression for different periods until 2022. These were complemented with data provided by the *Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico* for Spain (MITECO, 2023, 2024) and by the reports of timber-forest value chain for Galicia developed by the *Axencia Galega da Industria Forestal -XERA-* (Picos, 2018, 2022, 2023).

$$b = a(1 + x)^n; x = \sqrt[n]{\frac{b}{a}} - 1 \quad (1)$$

where: b = production in the last year of the period; a is the production in the first year of the period, n = number of years for the period, and x = annual rate (%).

2.2. HARDWOOD PRODUCTS FOR TIMBER CONSTRUCTION

According to the Construction Products Regulation, European standards (EN) were analysed under the technical committees *TC 124: Timber structures*, and *TC 112: Wood-based panels* of the European Standardisation Committee (CEN) with the aim to identify the mature hardwood products on the market in the Iberian Peninsula. Innovative hardwood products already on the market were also identified. To this end, the European Technical Assessments (ETA) of wood products, an alternative way to obtain the CE marking when harmonised EN standards are not available, were identified for the European Assessment Documents (EAD) under the product areas *PA 13: Structural timber products, elements and ancillaries*, *PA 14. Wood-based panels and elements*, and *PA 21. Wall and ceiling finishes and internal partition kits*, of the European Organisation of Technical Assessment (EOTA, 2023).

2.3. ANALYSIS OF THE RESILIENCE OF THE FOREST FOR THE CURRENT MARKETS. WORKSHOP IN GALICIA

The workshop was conducted in Lugo (Galicia) as part of an international symposium (XERA, 2024). The aim was to co-create knowledge on how stakeholders perceive and resolve the resilience trade-offs and challenges identified for the forestry production, the sawnwood industry, and the panel and pulp industries based on hardwood species. In view of these three industries, three discussion groups were organized with stakeholders from Galicia representing, among others, industrial and services companies, university institutes and technological research centres, and public administration. The three main questions discussed included: i) What are the main resilience challenges in the region?, ii) How can these challenges be overcome?, and iii) Which solutions and actions do we need and from whom?

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. OVERVIEW OF HARDWOOD PRODUCTION IN EU-27, SPAIN, AND GALICIA BY MARKETS

3.1.1 HARDWOOD REMOVALS IN 2022

In 2022, removals of both softwood and hardwood roundwood in EU-27, Spain (ES), and Galicia (GZ) in 2022 amounted to 508 MMm³ (165 MMm³ hardwoods), 21.4 MMm³ (9.7 MMm³ hardwoods) and 10.8 MMm³ (6.5 MMm³ hardwoods), respectively. Values for Europe and Spain were taken from the FAO database (FAO, 2023) and the values for Galicia were provided by XERA (Picos, 2023). While hardwoods, both native and exotic, accounted for 32% of total roundwood removals in the EU-27, this percentage rises to 45% in Spain and 60% in Galicia. 50% of the roundwood removals in Spain come from the Galician forests (Cluster da Madeira de Galicia, 2024). Table 1 shows the removals and industrial destinations of hardwood in EU-27 and ES in 2022.

When analysed by species, most of the hardwood removals in Spain in 2021 were *Eucalyptus* spp. (6.8 MMm³), followed by *Populus* spp. (0.5 MMm³), *Quercus robur* (0.14 MMm³), *Fagus sylvatica* (0.13 MMm³), *Castanea sativa* (0.10 MMm³), *Quercus rubra* (0.05 MMm³), and others (0.12 MMm³), (MITECO, 2024). Of these, 5.6 MMm³ of *Eucalyptus* spp., 0.2 MMm³ of broadleaves, and 0.02 MMm³ of other hardwoods (non-broadleaves, excluding *eucalyptus*) came from Galicia, according to the harvest applications submitted to the Consellería do Medio Rural of

Xunta de Galicia (Picos, 2022). In 2022, the harvest of eucalyptus logs in Galicia exceeded 6.2 MMm³, conifers did not reach 4.5 MMm³, and the rest of the species was around 0.3 MMm³ (Picos, 2023).

The forest-wood value chain accounts for almost 12% of industrial employment and 1.9% of GDP of Galicia (Cluster da Madeira de Galicia, 2024). The main markets in economic terms in 2022 were wood-based panels and pulp (1,055 MME), followed by sawnwood industry (465 MME), second transformation (607 MME) and biomass for energy (85 MME), (Picos, 2023).

Table 1. Total removals and production of hardwoods in EU-27 and Spain in 2022 (million m³), developed from FAO database

Domestic removals	Domestic removals by industrial use in 2022		Products
ROUNDWOOD: EU-27: 165 (517) ES: 8.54 (18.1) GZ ¹ : 6.5	WOODFUEL: EU-27: 87.9 (132) ES: 1.34 (3.75)		
	INDUSTRIAL ROUNDWOOD: EU-27: 76.7 (385) ES-FAO: 7.19 (14.4)	SAWLOGS & VENEER LOGS EU-27: 28.6 (227) ES: 0.73 (4.15)	- SAWWOOD PRODUCTION ³ : EU-27: 8.58 (109) ES: 0.62 (3.75) - VENEER SHEETS ^{2,3} : EU-27: (1.35) ES: (0.23)
		PULPWOOD, round and split EU-27: 45.3 (152) ES: 6.06 (9.81)	- WOOD-BASED PANELS ^{2,3} (fibreboard, particleboard, OSB, plywood) EU-27: (59.7) ES: (8.33) - PULP ^{2,3} : EU-27: (38 MM tonnes) ES: (XX)
		OTHER INDUSTRIAL ROUNDWOOD EU-27: 2.85 (6.75) ES: 0.14 (0.40)	

¹ GZ: Galicia (Picos, 2023); ² Not differentiated between softwoods and hardwoods in FAO database; ³ No data from MITECO

NOTE: The total softwood + hardwood production is shown between brackets ().

3.1.2 DYNAMICS IN HARDWOODS VS. SOFTWOODS REMOVALS

The dynamics between 2005 and 2022 in removals and production of hardwoods were studied and compared with those of softwoods. Figure 2 shows the dynamics and annual rates of roundwood removals in Europe, Spain and Galicia. While in Europe the removals of softwoods have been significantly higher than those of hardwoods over the last 17 years, in Spain the removals of softwoods and hardwoods have been similar, and in Galicia the removals of hardwoods have been significantly higher than softwoods. This trend for Galicia is due to the incidence of the introduced Eucalyptus spp., mainly used for pulp and paper, which also influences the trends in Spain.

Figure 2. Dynamics and annual rates (%) of roundwood removals in EU-27 (from FAO database), Spain, and Galicia (from MITECO database)

As the values vary depending on the source, a comparison was made between the data provided by FAO, MITECO and XERA for the last 7 years (data available from all the sources considered) as shown in Table 2. The values provided by MITECO and XERA are very similar, while FAO provides higher wood volumes than MITECO, with 15% being the mean value of the relative difference.

Table 2. Comparison of hardwood roundwood removals (1000 m³) data from FAO, MITECO and XERA databases.

Year	SPAIN			GALICIA		
	FAO	MITECO	Relative difference (%)	MITECO	XERA	Relative difference (%)
2017	8.974	8.091	10	5.690	5.319	7
2018	10.164	9.104	10	6.170	6.152	0
2019	10.084	8.085	20	5.869	5.712	3
2020	9.870	7.545	24	5.562	5.452	2
2021	9.389	7.824	17	5.846	5.845	0
2022	9.767	8.661	11	6.553	6.41	1
Mean			15			2

The dynamics and annual rates of hardwood removals by industrial use in Europe and Spain are shown in Figure 3. In the absence of MITECO data for industrial uses, FAO database was used for the analysis. The main industrial use in both the European and Spanish cases is for pulp logs (pulp industry and wood-based panel industry), although in Spain it is increasing at a higher annual rate.

Figure 3. Dynamics in industrial roundwood removals by destiny in EU-27 and Spain, both developed from FAO database

3.2. HARDWOOD MARKETS

3.2.1. SAWWOOD

In 2022, hardwoods in the EU-27 accounted for only 8% of the total sawnwood production (8 MMm³). Spain has been one of the top ten hardwood producers since 2009, with a hardwood share of total sawnwood production (17%) higher than the European average. Sawn hardwood production in Europe and Spain has been falling since 1995, although production was constant between 2010 and 2019. While the main market for softwoods is wood construction (EOS, 2023) and pallet and wooden packaging (UN, 2016), hardwoods are used for furniture, interiors and flooring. In Galicia, Eucalyptus is mainly used for mussel farms and laminated profiles for carpentry. Native broadleaves, with almost no forest management, are mainly used for firewood (mostly sweet chestnut, with more than 25.000 tonnes), the construction sector, railway sleepers, staves for barrels and furniture (Rodríguez Soalleiro, 2024).

3.2.2. WOOD-BASED PANELS

The main products of the wood-based panel industry in the EU-27 are particleboard (50%) and fibreboard (30%), (FAO, 2023), which are primarily used in furniture manufacturing. However, the FAO database does not distinguish between hardwoods and softwoods. 21 Spanish industries are members of the European Panel Federation (EPF, 2024), 6 of these produce particleboard, mainly melamine-faced panels for furniture applications (3 plants in GZ), 4 produce medium-density fibreboard (MDF) primarily for export (4 plants in GZ), 1 produces hardboard (1 plant in GZ) and 13 produce plywood, mainly from poplar for furniture and packaging followed by transport and construction (no plant in GZ). In Galicia, fibreboard panels are made from both *Pinus spp.* and *Eucalyptus spp.*, while particleboard is principally produced from pine (Rodríguez Soalleiro, 2024).

3.2.3. PULP

The production of wood pulp in 2022 in the EU-27 was 38 MMt (FAO, 2023). 95% of wood pulp was chemical and mechanical pulp, with the main destinations being packaging paper (61%), printing and writing (23%), and household and sanitary paper (8%). 5% of the wood pulp was dissolving pulp, an emerging market using hardwood species for the textile industry, bioplastics, and pharmaceuticals. Softwoods are the main species used for packaging

paper, while hardwoods are mainly used for printing and writing paper, household and sanitary paper and dissolving pulp (Dieste et al., 2019). In Galicia, wood pulp is the main destination for *Eucalyptus ssp.*

3.3. HARDWOOD PRODUCTS FOR WOOD CONSTRUCTION

Table 3 shows the mature hardwood products on the market in Spain and their corresponding hEN, differentiating whether the origin is from Galicia (GZ) or from other regions of Spain (ES). It includes five sawn hardwoods approved for use in structural applications, and different types of wood-based panels (OSB, fibreboard, plywood, solid wood panels and LVL) manufactured from different hardwood species, primarily for non-structural applications.

Table 3. Mature hardwood products in the construction market under CEN

TC	Product	EN	Species	Origin	
				ES	GZ
TC 124. Structural timber	Structurally graded cross-section sawnwood	UNE 56546	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> ¹	×	✓
		EN 1912	<i>Eucalyptus nitens</i>	×	✓
			<i>Castanea sativa</i>	✓	✓
TC 112. Wood-based panels	Oriented Strand Boards (OSB) Fibreboards Hardwoods plywood Solid wood panels (SWP) for structural design SWP of hardwoods for appearance use Cement-bonded particleboards Laminated Veneer Lumber (LVL)	EN 300	S/H ⁴ (poplar, ...)	✓	×
		EN 622	S/H ⁴ (eucalyptus spp., ...)	✓	✓
		EN 365-2	(poplar, eucalyptus, oak,...)	✓	×
		EN 12369-3	S/H ⁴	×	×
		EN 13017-2	(sweet chestnut, oak, beech,...)	✓	✓
		EN 1328	S/H ⁴	×	×
		EN 14279	S/H ⁴ (eucalyptus spp., ...)	✓	×

¹Wood from GZ and Portugal ²(Moltini G. et al., 2021), (Martin Bacher, 2022); ³(Moltini et al., 2024);

⁴S&H: EN standard applies to both softwoods and hardwoods. Some examples are included between brackets

3.3.1 VISUAL STRUCTURALLY GRADED SPECIES

Four hardwood species are included in the national visual grading standard UNE 56546 (AENOR, 2024), namely Southern blue gum (*Eucalyptus globulus*), shining gum (*Eucalyptus nitens*), sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), and black poplar (*Populus x euroamericana*, clones MC and Luisa Avanzo). Hardwood species are visually graded as MEF (*Madera Estructural de Frondosas* / Hardwood structural timber) or MEF-G (*Madera Estructural de Frondosas de Gran Escuadria* / Large cross-section hardwood structural timber). Table 4 shows the visual grades for the testing type, the characteristic values for strength (f_k in bending or in tension parallel to the grain), mean values for modulus of elasticity (E_m , in bending or in tension) and both mean (σ_m) and characteristic (σ_k) values for density; and the assigned strength class in EN 1912 (CEN, 2023).

Table 4. Visual grades and strength classes of Spanish hardwood species (developed from UNE 56544 (AENOR, 2024), EN 1912 (CEN, 2023), and EN 338 (CEN, 2016))

Species	Cross-section (mm)	Visual grade	Testing	Properties				Strength classes assigned in EN 1912
				f_k (N/mm ²)	E_m (N/mm ²)	σ_m (Kg/m ³)	σ_k (Kg/m ³)	
Sweet chestnut	b≤70	MEF	bending	28.1	12290	582	510	D27
	b:≤160; h:≤160	MEF-G	bending	26.8	10280	582	500	D24
Southern blue gum	b≤60; h≤200	MEF	bending	46.4	18430	797	673	D40
Shinning gum	-	MEF	bending	36.7	13834	612	465	C35
		MEF	tension	24.3	14049	612	465	T24
Poplar	-	MEF	tension	10.9	8534	392	340	-

Southern blue gum shows the highest strength class (D40), followed by shining gum (C35), both obtained from bending tests. Its low characteristic value of density (465 Kg/m^3) did not reach the minimum value required for the assignment of the lowest strength class for hardwoods D18 (475 kg/m^3); therefore, a C class was assigned. Currently, the strength classes for hardwood species tested in tension are not yet allowed in EN 338 (CEN, 2016). However, the low-density values of shining gum allowed the assignment to a strength class T24 for softwood species. Sweet chestnut shows lower values of strength and modulus of elasticity than shining gum, but higher density. Depending on its cross-section, the strength class is D27 or D24. Black poplar tested in tension has been incorporated in 2024 to the visual grading standard and shows the structural properties. Although the assignment to a strength class is not yet included in EN 1912, it could be classified as T10 for softwood species tested in tension. Except for poplar, specimens of Galician origin were represented in the sampling of the visual grading of Spanish hardwoods.

3.3.2. MACHINE STRUCTURALLY GRADED SPECIES

In addition, two species, Southern blue gum and beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), have been machine graded according to EN 14081-2 (CEN, 2019), and approved by the Task Group TG1 for visual and machine grading of the technical committee *TC124:Timber Structures/WG2:Solid Wood*. The yield of machine grading is generally higher than that of visual grading in terms of the number of strength class combinations, higher strength class achieved, and the percentage of samples classified in the higher strength classes (Moltini, Íñiguez-González, et al., 2022). However, their strength classes are not included in any national or European standard. The values remain confidential for the *CEN/TC124/WG2/TG1*, the owners of the grading machines, and the authors of the reports. Southern blue gum from Galicia and Portugal was the first machine graded hardwood species with strength classes assigned from tensile tests which was approved by CEN. A total of seven strength classes combinations was obtained using the grading machines Viscan (©Microtec, Bressanone, Italy) and MTG (©Brookhuis, Enschede, The Netherlands), (Bacher et al., 2022; Moltini, Baño, et al., 2022). The strength classes were defined for the three fundamental properties of tensile strength and modulus of elasticity and density. Beech from Northeast of Spain was machine graded into seven strength combinations (Moltini et al., 2024). Table 5 shows the strength classes combinations for both species depending on the grading machine.

Table 5. Strength classes combinations machine graded hardwood species in Spain (developed from (Bacher et al., 2022; CEN, 2016; Moltini, Baño, et al., 2022; Moltini et al., 2024))

Species	Origin	Cross-section (mm)	Grading machine	Testing	Strength classes' combinations		
Southern blue gum	Portugal and Galicia (ES)	b: 20-32	VISCAN	tension	ET42/ET34/ET28	ET42/ET24	ET34
					T42/ET34/ET24	ET38/ET24	
		h: 81-154	MTG	tension	ET42/ET34/ET28	ET42/ET30	ET38/ET24
					T42/ET34/ET24	ET42/ET24	ET34
Beech	Navarre (ES)	b: 23-49	MTG	bending	D50/D35/D24	D40/D27	D35/D24
					D50/D30	D40/D24	D30
		h: 63-159			D50/D27		

In general, small cross-sections are mainly used for manufacturing glued laminated products, such as glulam, or for light framing. Larger cross-sections, such as sweet chestnut graded as MEF-G, is mainly used for heavy wood framing, which is typical for ancient buildings in Galicia. Table 6 shows the innovative hardwood products on the market and their corresponding EAD by Product Area, including hardwoods glulam.

EN standard for hardwood glulam was not yet approved by CEN, however there is two manufacturers of hardwoods glulam in Spain with ETA certification. Since it is not possible to assign them strength classes, the

characteristic values of the physical and mechanical properties are provided in the Declaration of Performance (DoP). The values for chestnut glulam, produced by Sierolam (Asturias, Spain) are: $f_{m,k}=30 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{t,0,k}=20 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{c,0,k}=45 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{v,k}=5 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $E_{0,m} = 13000 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $G_{mean}=810 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $G_{r,05}=65 \text{ N/mm}^2$, and $\sigma_k=540 \text{ Kg/m}^3$; showing higher strength than sawnwood (Table 4). The properties for oak, produced by Gámiz (Vitoria, Basque Country) are: $f_{m,k}=33 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{t,0,k}=23 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{t,90,k}=0.6$, $f_{c,0,k}=45 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $f_{c,90,k}=8$, $f_{v,k}=4 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $E_{0,m} = 14400 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $E_{90,m} = 800 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $G_{mean}=850 \text{ N/mm}^2$, and $\sigma_k=690 \text{ Kg/m}^3$. Oak shows properties slightly higher than those for sweet chestnut.

Table 6. Innovative hardwood products in the construction market under EOTA

PA	Product	EAD	Product/species	Figures	Origin	
					ES	GZ
PA 13	Glued laminated timber made from solid hardwood	130320-00-0304	SIEROLAM		✓	✗
			(Castanea sativa) VIGAM		✓	✗
	(Quercus robur)					
	Structural Composite Lumber Product- Laminated Strand Lumber (LSL)	130308-00-0304	LIGNUMSTRAND (Poplar)		✓	✗
	Composite wood-based beams and columns	130367-00-0304	ECOTIMBERCELL ¹ (eucalyptus hardboard)		✗	✓
PA 14	Pre-fabricated wood-based loadbearing stressed skin panels	140022-00-0304	ECOTIMBERCELL BOX ¹		✗	✓
PA 21	Fibreboards for non-structural indoor uses made of recycled cellulosic fibres from industrial cellulosic residues.	210132-00-0504	Honext board ²		✓	✗
	Self-Supporting composite lightweight panels used as an EAD	ETAG 001 used as EAD	CALIPLAC ¹ , THERMOCHIP ¹ , TEZNO ¹		✓	✗

¹ Some elements can be made from hardwoods; ²can be made from both softwoods and hardwoods;

PA 13. Structural timber products; PA 14. Wood based panels; PA 21. Wall and ceiling finishes and internal partitions

3.4. MAIN CHALLENGES IN GALICIA FOR THE FOREST MANAGEMENT AND THE WOOD INDUSTRY.

The main resilience challenges were identified in a workshop with Galician stakeholders for the whole forest-wood value chain (forest management, solid wood and engineered wood products industry, and other industries, including wood-based panels, biorefineries and others), Table 7.

Table 7. Main challenges, proposed measured and essential steps in forest management, solid wood, and other industries

	Main challenges	Proposed measures	Essential steps, keys to success
Forest management	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) fragmented, abandoned forest properties 2) low profitability of native hardwoods timber harvesting 3) need to adapt forest stands to climate change 4) socio-economic model to finance adaptation measures and to share costs and benefits 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) grouping/association of forest management units & use rights; 2) motivation and incentivisation of landowners for management (taxes) 3) active management of existing native hardwoods areas, both for conservation and for production, and establish new hardwoods areas 4) landscape level management in forestry and agroforestry to address risk, disturbances and adaptation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) review the taxation system related to forest management to allow for lower tax burden as incentive for active management 2) communication with society and forest owners 3) coordination between forest management and the whole forest value chain.
Solid wood and EWP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) development of higher added-value products 2) ensure the fair benefit distribution 3) small diameter and curved logs in native hardwoods 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) implementation of comprehensive strategies addressing social and technical dimensions of forest management 2) update legislation facilitating the hardwoods harvesting 3) education and skills in wood construction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) update legislation facilitating native hardwoods harvesting 2) cooperation between all the sectors involved in the forest value chain 3) institutional support to hardwood forest management 4) using more wood in housing 5) Standardization and incentives in GPP
Panels, biorefineries, other	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) small size of forest plots 2) existing biorefineries lack experience in working with native hardwoods 3) lack of stable hardwoods mobilization 4) difficulty to move from pilot tests to market 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) public-private cooperation 2) innovative public procurement 3) forest management aligned with forest industry 4) communication with other sectors related to bioproducts 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) administration facilitating discussion spaces 2) cooperation between industry and research centres and university 3) identification of existing innovations

4. CONCLUSIONS

The growing stock of broadleaved forests in Europe increased at a higher rate than coniferous forests, but the industrial uses of hardwoods only represent 20% of the total industrial roundwood. In the EU-27, 32% of domestic removals are hardwoods, of which 53% are used directly for wood energy purposes. In Spain, hardwoods represent 47% of domestic removals, with only 16% used in wood energy. The major share (76%) of hardwood removals in Spain originate from Galicia. *Eucalyptus spp.* accounts for 87% of total hardwoods harvested in Spain, mainly used in the pulp industry. In Spain, the wood pulp industries absorb a higher proportion of hardwoods (85%) compared to the European average (59%). On the other hand, the sawnwood industry accounts for much lower shares of volume (10% in Spain vs. 37% in EU-27). The shares of hardwood removals excluding *Eucalyptus spp.* is 16% in Spain, while in Galicia it represents only 5%. Overall, Galicia represents a quite underdeveloped market for hardwoods in terms of volumes and diversification.

Given the still limited utilisation of hardwoods in the construction sector, a growing interest from companies and public actors can be observed to integrate them into more building projects in Spain. The structural properties of

Spanish chestnut, eucalyptus (both *E. globulus* and *E. nitens*), and beech timber have been included in the European standards. The availability, aesthetics, and natural durability of sweet chestnut and oak, among other qualities, has led to their commercialisation as glulam products for structural uses. The absence of an approved European standard to produce hardwood glulam for structural purposes, has led to the marketing of glulam products from these species via the European Technical Assessment (ETA-EOTA) certification.

Except for poplar, hardwood species in Spain show higher mechanical properties than softwoods. Southern blue gum, beech, and sweet chestnut reached strength classes D40, D50, and D27 respectively, which are considerably higher than the common C24 strength class of spruce. Glulam of native hardwoods, such as chestnut and oak, are already commercialised in Europe via ETA certification, revealing the interest to use them in timber structures.

Fragmented and abandoned forest properties, negligence of management of hardwood forests, administrative limitations on hardwoods harvesting, and lack of established industries for added-value products are the main challenges identified in Galicia. Creation of new native hardwoods plantation areas, integrating agroforestry and forest management, and fostering public-private cooperation between different actors in the whole value chain are amongst the promising solutions identified to overcome these challenges.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The present work was developed in the framework of the Horizon Europe projects EUFORE “European Forest Research and Innovation Ecosystem” grant no. 101081788 and RESONATE “Resilient forest value chains” grant no. 101000574, funded by the European Commission.

REFERENCES

- AENOR. (2024). UNE 56546. Clasificación visual de la madera aserrada para uso estructural. Madera de frondosas (Visual grading of structural sawn timber. Hardwoods).
- Asada, R., Hurmekoski, E., Hoeben, A. D., Patacca, M., Stern, T., & Toppinen, A. (2023). Resilient forest-based value chains? Econometric analysis of roundwood prices in five European countries in the era of natural disturbances. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2023.102975>
- Bacher, M., Fontanini, F., Moltini, G., & Baño, V. (2022). TGI/202204/15_rev.1. VISCAN. Derivation of machine settings according to EN14081-2 for Southern blue gum in Spain and Portugal tested in tension.
- CEN. (2016). EN 338. Structural timber. Strength classes. European Standardisation Committee.
- CEN. (2019). EN 14081-2. Timber structures. Strength graded structural timber with rectangular cross section. Part 2: Machine grading. Additional requirements for type testing.
- CEN. (2023). prEN 1912:2023. Structural Timber - Strength classes - Assignment of visual grades and species. CEN TC 124 WG 2.
- Cluster da Madeira de Galicia. (2024, July 8). Main magnitudes of the sector. <https://Clustermadeira.Com/Magintudes-Sector/>.
- Dieste, A., Cabrera, M. N., Clavijo, L., Cassella, N., Dieste, A., Cabrera, M. N., Clavijo, L., & Cassella, N. (2019). Analysis of wood products from an added value perspective: The Uruguayan forestry case. *Maderas. Ciencia y Tecnología*, 21(ahead), 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-221X2019005000303>
- EOS. (2023). ANNUAL REPORT 2022-2023 OF THE EUROPEAN SAWMILL INDUSTRY. <https://eos-oes.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/eos-annual-report-20222023.pdf>
- EOTA. (2023, February 2). ETA database. <https://Www.Eota.Eu/Etassessments>. <https://www.eota.eu/etassessments>
- EPF. (2024). European Panel Federation. Annual Report 2023-2024.
- EU. (2022). Revised Construction Products Regulation. Factsheet. In Publications Office of the European Union. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2873/46052>
- EU. (2024, July 10). New European Bauhaus initiative. https://New-European-Bauhaus.Europa.Eu/about/about-Initiative_en.
- European Parliament. (2024). DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275. Energy performance of buildings.
- European Commission. (2023, November 7). Interactive Sankey diagrams of woody biomass flows in the EU and Member States. https://Knowledge4policy.Ec.Europa.Eu/Visualisation/Interactive-Sankey-Diagrams-Woody-Biomass-Flows-Eu-Member-States_en.
- FAO. (2023, November 7). FAOSTAT. Forestry Production and Trade. <https://Www.Fao.Org/Faostat/En/#data/FO>.
- Forest Europe. (2021). State of Europe’s Forests 2020. www.foresteurope.org

- Hlásny, T., Zimová, S., Merganičová, K., Štěpánek, P., Modlinger, R., & Turčáni, M. (2021). Devastating outbreak of bark beetles in the Czech Republic: Drivers, impacts, and management implications. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 490, 119075. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2021.119075>
- Martin Bacher, F. F. G. M. y V. B. (2022). TG1/202204/15. Derivation of machine settings according to EN 14081-2:2018 for Southern blue gum grown in Spain and Portugal tested in tension. Confidential to CEN TC124 WG2 TG1.
- MITECO. (2023). Advance of the forestry statistics yearbook 2022 Spain. <https://www.miteco.gob.es/content/dam/miteco/es/biodiversidad/estadisticas/anuario-estadistica-forestal-2022-avance.pdf>
- MITECO. (2024, July 8). Annual Timber Harvesting Statistics. https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/estadisticas/forestal_estad_anual_cortas_madera.html.
- Moltini, G., Azaña, M., & Villanueva, J. L. (2024). Report TG1/202404/14. Derivation of machine settings for D-classes of European beech from Spain according to EN 14081-2:2018. In Report confidential to CEN TC124 WG2 TG1. CEN.
- Moltini G., Baño V., Martins C., & Dias A. (2021). TG1/2021/11/03_03. Derivation of MTG machine settings of Southern blue gum from Spain and Portugal tested in tension according to EN 14081-2:2018. Confidential to CEN TC124 WG2 TG1. In CEN TC124 WG2 TG1.
- Moltini, G., Baño, V., Martins, C., & Dias, A. (2022). TG1/2021/11/03_rev.3. Derivation of MTG machine settings of Southern blue gum from Spain and Portugal tested in tension according to EN 14081-2.
- Moltini, G., Íñiguez-González, G., Cabrera, G., & Baño, V. (2022). Evaluation of Yield Improvements in Machine vs. Visual Strength Grading for Softwood Species. *Forests*, 13(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/f13122021>
- Patacca, M., Lindner, M., Nabuurs, G. J., & Schelhaas, M.-J. (2023). EFI Policy Brief 4. Significant increase in forest disturbances since 1950s. <https://efi.int/publications-bank/significant-increase-forest-disturbances-1950s>
- Picos, J. (2018). La cadena Forestal-Madera de Galicia 2017. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17809.48487>
- Picos, J. (2022). La cadena forestal-madera de Galicia 2021. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367203918>
- Picos, J. (2023). La cadena forestal-madera de Galicia 2022. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31367.16801>
- Rodríguez Soalleiro, R. (2024). Broadleaves in Galicia. In Presentation at the international symposium “Native hardwoods: the resilience of the forest sector?” hosted by Galician Agency for Forest-based Industry · XERA · Xunta de Galicia in Lugo, Spain on Feb 28 to March 1, 2024 .
- Schelhaas, M. J., Fridman, J., Hengeveld, G. M., Henttonen, H. M., Lehtonen, A., Kies, U., Krajnc, N., Lerink, B., Dhubbáin, Á. N., Polley, H., Pugh, T. A. M., Redmond, J. J., Rohner, B., Temperli, C., Vayreda, J., & Nabuurs, G. J. (2018). Actual European forest management by region, tree species and owner based on 714,000 re-measured trees in national forest inventories. *PLoS ONE*, 13(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0207151>
- UN. (2016). Trends and perspectives for pallets and wooden packaging.
- XERA. (2024). Simposio “Las frondosas autóctonas, ¿la resiliencia del sector forestal?” In <https://xera.xunta.gal/es/a-axencia/simposio-frondosas-2024>. XERA.